

Interview Vasiliki Argyropoulos / UNIWA
29.10.2021 / 1h30

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Updated: 2021-07-28

WP2. Investigating the conservation of WWII wrecks (land or underwater), and more particularly parts made of Al alloys_ Guidelines for interviews.

- Short presentation of interviewee :

Vasiliki Argyropoulos has a background as a chemical engineer, has then moved towards metals conservation.

Experience with WWII aircraft wrecks through two projects :

- 1st project with the Tatoi Museum in 2002-2003
- 2nd project : pieces from WWII plane in 2004

1st project :

Project concerned the recovery of a German aircraft, located in the sea near Leros. Leros was the last major battle in Greece in 1943, between British and Italian alliance and German forces ; the Germans won, very strategic island.

Various wrecks ships and aircrafts all around the island from this battle. Deep waters.

Vasiliki had been called to carry out treatment after recovery, electrolytical treatment based on C. Degrin's protocole. Her recommendation was to leave the wreck in the water. Put « political » pushback to raise it, as it was a more sensationnal outcome. In the end, the wreck has been lifted and has been treated with acid treatment, recommended by another professor

2nd project :

The project concerned treatment of dechlorination on pieces from WWII aircraft, in 2004. But after analysis, the team couldn't find any chlorides in the water, so no treatment performed.

- Legal framework in Greece :

In the water, the Ministry of Culture owns everything older than 50 years old, except if the Ministry of Defense is involved.

The Ministry of Defence has natural ownership of the wreck if it's one of their battle ships. If the wreck is from another country, it belongs to the flag nation unless the country relinquishes it. But some countries state that it automatically belongs to them and don't have to claim it.

Framework is more complicated when situations of danger or the wreck blocks sea passage.

The right procedure would be to contact flag nation in any case, but that is not always the case.

Vasiliki is not familiar with regulations for wrecks on land, recommends to talk to the Airforce.

After WWII, law in Greece authorized people to recover and take wrecks for the metal, as people were very poor at the time. That was done a lot and many wrecks have been dismantled and reused ; but maybe not so much for Al parts, or wrecks in deep waters.

- The operating chain: from the wreck to the museum

At what stage or stages of the operating chain has (or is) the institution/ group / association been involved ? Defining a recovery project ? Integrating wrecks or artefacts from wrecks in the collection ? Do they have direct input in defining the projects or just executing ? What is their approach ? Is it similar or different approach if different projects ?

Generally speaking in Greece, the operating chain organization for archeological finds depends on who the wreck belongs to and if it's considered as heritage. If yes, need for conservation plan to be validated by the responsible body. Rules apply for outdoor heritage older than 100 years, which is not yet the case for WWII heritage.

Aircraft most of the time is not considered as heritage, it belongs to the Ministry of Defense, who has entire responsibility on the orientation of the project and are usually less focused on conservation. Their people have more usually profiles from aircraft industry or mechanics.

- Concept of "conservation" : Do you think of long-term preservation/conservation of the artefacts you handle ? How do you define long term ? What does the idea of "conservation" mean to you for this kind of heritage ? How would you want that heritage to be passed on to future generations ? Has that definition shifted over time for you/the institution ?

Not involved in conservation

- Who works on these collections (after recovery) : conservators, technical staff (aviation background or not), volunteers? What training for these different stakeholders? Do they work in collaboration? Are they internal or external to the museum? What is the relationship between museum management / conservation and the people in charge of interventions directly ? (addition to Form A)

Mainly technical staff coming from aviation/mechanical background, sometimes conservators. Not so much with volunteers.

Aviation Archaeology : is an association of volunteers, but they work underwater, no recovery.

Icaros Foundation¹ : Public Benefit Foundation established in 2017, associated to a famous school of flying, under patronage of Hellenic Air Force.

Are devoted to returning WWII aircrafts to flying condition. In 2018, have carried supervised the restoration to flying condition of a Supermarine Spitfire fighter. Rebuilding and restoration carried out by a British company, The Spitfire Company (Biggin Hill) Ltd. In 2021, have been commissioned by the Hellenic Air Force General Staff for a second restoration to flying condition, for a T-6 Harvard, also belonging to the Hellenic Air Force Museum, also with the same company in the UK.

- Conditions of conservation of the collection / artefact : aircraft in working order with regular maintenance / complete planes (or nearly) with or without preventive conservation / wrecks or elements of wrecks: exposed or not, kept in storage /outdoors (addition to Form A) ?

Vassiliki is not involved in conservation

¹ <https://www.haf.gr/en/2018/09/restoration-hafs-supermarine-spitfire-mj755-aircraft/>
<https://warbirdsnews.com/warbird-restorations/greek-spitfire-resurfaces-at-biggin-hill.html>
<https://en.protothema.gr/second-historic-haf-airplane-to-be-restored-to-flying-status-photos/>
<https://www.thenationalherald.com/greek-historic-spitfire-fighter-to-soar-in-the-skies-again/>

- Conditions of storage location (exhibition room or storage) : rooms or hall ? awareness about influence of climate on preservation ? Monitoring or not of HR & T ° and their changes during the year (addition to Form A) ?

Vassiliki is not involved in conservation

- Reflecting on their own practice : do you feel that you know everything you would like to when it comes to managing this sort of artefacts ? What would be the aspects you would like to know more about ? Do you keep informed or in contact with other stakeholders in this field ? Has your practice evolved through those connections ?

Vassiliki is not involved in conservation

- Conservation problem that may be encountered with Al alloys (questions and needs if there are any, or practices for solving these problems) ? Does it feel like a priority concern regarding your corpus of WWII wrecks ? regarding the rest of the collection (if relevant) ? What type of treatment protocols are (or have been) carried out (addition to Form A) ?

Vassiliki is interested in Al conservation issues, but mainly in terms of painted surfaces.
She has no idea on how to preserve this kind of objects with corrosion under paint.
She has worked mainly on examples out of Procraft timeframe (planes 1st flight in 1964).

- Promotion of WWII aeronautical heritage, influence of the country's history in the conflict and the relationship to that history ?

October 28th is "DAY of NO": commemorates the refuse of Greece to surrender to Italy during WWII.
Caused invasion by German forces
Lot of commemoration events this day.

Also, in general, yearly commemorations of WWII battles, monuments in various locations. Lots of emotions related to this period.
Maybe more attachment for ships, as they have caused more deaths when lost. Even when it involves other countries.
Planes are more seen in the water, not so much as recovered wrecks.

During WWII, Italians gave up arms and joined the Greeks, but not the Germans.

People are very proud in Greece to have been on the side of Allies, a lot of planes on display related to WWII. In terms of German heritage : not so strong rejection anymore nowadays. Maybe not commemorations associated with the German planes.

Not the same kind of respect for Greek and foreign heritage in general. In Greece not so much value for Turkish heritage.

Also so much more ancient heritage to prioritize compared to more recent heritage.

Airforce museum : Vassiliki will make first contact and fill questionnaire and Form A.